

The Green Accounting of Small Medium Business Fashion's Sector in West Java

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Abstract:- The aims of the study was to analyze the level of understanding and application of Green Accounting in the financial statements of small and medium fashion businesses in Bekasi and to determine the effect of the level of understanding and application of Green Accounting in the financial statements of small and medium fashion business in Bekasi. The results showed that the level of understanding of Green Accounting in Bekasi fashion SMEs has a good assessment. This is evidenced by the answers of some respondents who answered agree. Means everything that is felt, perceived by respondents about the level of understanding of Green Accounting in Bekasi fashion SMEs. The application of Green Accounting in Bekasi fashion SMEs has a good assessment. The level of understanding of Green Accounting has a positive effect on the financial statements of Bekasi fashion SMEs. This shows that the higher the level of understanding of Green Accounting has a positive effect on financial statements. The application of Green Accounting has a positive influence on the financial statements of Bekasi fashion SMEs. This shows that the higher the level of application of Green Accounting has a positive effect on the financial statements.

Keywords:- Green Accounting, Fashion, Understanding, Application and SMEs

I. INTRODUCTION

Green Accounting a new paradigm in accounting that focuses on the accounting process not only on financial transactions, events or objects, but on social and environmental objects, transactions or events.

Loko (2018) defines Green Accounting as the process of recognizing, measuring value, recording, summarizing reporting and disclosing information on objects, transactions, events, or the impact of corporate economic, social and environmental activities on society and the environment and the corporation itself in one package. reporting of integrated accounting information so that it can be useful for users in assessing and making economic and non-economic decisions.

Ahmad et al., (2017) defining the application of Green Accounting is the process of recognizing, measuring value, recording, summarizing reporting and disclosing information on objects, transactions, events, or the impact of corporate

economic, social and environmental activities on society and the environment and the corporation itself in one accounting information reporting package integrated so that it can be useful for users in assessing and making economic and non-economic decisions (ByzzaNthi and Ermawati, 2021).

Endiana et al., (2020) explained that the role of the accounting sector in efforts to preserve the environment in the form of environmental costs and sustainable management in improving company performance. Good application of Green Accounting by companies is a positive thing that companies have in the eyes of stakeholders, because with good implementation of environmental accounting, the company has paid attention to the environmental impact around the company and the company is considered not only focused on maximizing profits in order to increase company profitability.

Understanding and applying Green Accounting can improve environmental performance with environmental resource decisions (Almaliki, 2020). This includes allocating environmental costs, measuring and aggregating costs with business (Şimsek and Ozturk, 2021). The application of Green Accounting is not only for large-scale entities but is very possible to be applied to the Small and Medium Enterprises (UKM) sector, then the term UKM will be used which is considered to have an obligation to understand and apply the concept of Application of Green Accounting in carrying out its business activities, because the contribution of SMEs other than as a contributors to the country's economy, also play a role in producing waste which can sometimes pollute and damage the environment.

Bekasi is an area that is in great demand by business people to open a business here, especially at night and on holidays, many business actors from outside the area come and take advantage here. Based on Table 1.2, it is explained that in the fashion sub-sector, there were 53 out of 60 SMEs that were dropped due to bankruptcy or non-production. As for the food and beverage sector, there were 341 sectors and in the service sector, there were 167 SMEs.

This research was conducted on SMEs in the fashion sector because the development of SMEs in the fashion sector experienced slower growth than other sectors. The results of observations and short interviews with fashion SMEs can be said that entrepreneurs still have problems in operating their

businesses, including low business productivity due to difficulties in financing or capital, low entrepreneur skills and sub-optimal marketing, if this is allowed to continue can lead to low business performance and even lead to business closure.

The phenomenon that occurs in the field, SMEs pay less attention to handling environmental waste, because they are more concerned with profit and turnover in their business activities, SMEs pay more attention to the quality of the products they produce so that spending on environmental costs is often ignored. Pentiana (2019) that SMEs only focus on operating profits, there is no awareness of environmental impacts that will affect business continuity, low knowledge of environmental costs because business actors have not been able to identify the components of environmental costs.

SMEs concern for the environment is low because there is no awareness of environmental impacts. Sukirman et al (2021) said that SMEs are aware of environmental protection issues, but their commitment to environmental protection is still low. Some SMEs cause environmental damage due to waste disposal which is still carried out haphazardly, such as in some fashion producing SMEs. It is undeniable that the production operations of SME fashion producers can have a negative impact on the environment if not handled properly, and can result in a decrease in the quality of the surrounding environment, such as soil, water and air pollution.

Several previous studies regarding the understanding and application of Green Accounting in SMEs. Hamidi (2019) found the application of Green Accounting companies can improve the company's environmental performance which ends in improving financial performance with environmental benefits that can be managed and preserved properly according to government regulations. Ashari and Anggoro (2021) found that the application of Green Accounting has an effect on the sustainability of small businesses. Shah and Bhatt (2022) found that the application of Green Accounting was implemented to benefit the industrial environment. Hossain (2019) found that the application of green accounting has cost constraints, lack of human resources, incorrect principles and low adoption of green accounting. Jaamani (2013) said that SMEs are aware of environmental protection issues, but their commitment to environmental protection is still low. Some SMEs cause environmental damage due to waste disposal which is still carried out haphazardly, such as in some SMEs producing fashion.

This research is important to do, especially regarding the understanding and application of Green Accounting in fashion SMEs in Bekasi, which has never been done in previous research, namely in terms of understanding and applying Green Accounting in the form of costs related to the environment incurred by fashion SMEs during the process of producing Fashion so as to produce financial reports adjusted to SAK EMKM. In addition, empirical knowledge is known in the form of external accounting reporting models and functions by

integrating financial and non-financial information reporting in the form of Green Accounting in the SME sector, especially fashion businesses.

The aims of research were 1) to determine the effect of the level of understanding of Green Accounting on the financial statements of small and medium fashion businesses in Bekasi; 2) to analyze the effect of implementing Green Accounting on the financial statements of small and medium fashion businesses in Bekasi.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Green Accounting Theory*

According to Aviany (2015), Green Accounting is a type of environmental accounting that describes efforts to incorporate environmental benefits and costs into making economic decisions or a business financial result, Green Accounting describes efforts to incorporate environmental benefits and costs into making economic decisions.

Monsnja and Grzinic (2019) explain Green Accounting is considered an important tool for understanding aspects of the natural environment that affect the economy and at the same time as an agent of sustainability. The aims of Green Accounting/environmental accounting is to inform about the operational performance of companies based on protection and concern for the environment, so that companies cannot process resources arbitrarily without regard to the impact on society. According to Cohen and Robbins, (2011), Green Accounting or environmental accounting is defined as:

“A style of accounting that includes the indirect costs and benefits of economic activity-such as environmental effects and health consequences of business decisions and plans”

Environmental is a type of accounting that includes the indirect costs and benefits of economic activity, such as the environmental impacts and health consequences of business planning and decisions. According to Aniela, (2012) Green Accounting is accounting in which it identifies, measures, presents, and discloses costs associated with company activities related to the environment.

➤ *Level of Understanding of Green Accounting*

Daryanto (2018) that understanding (comprehension) is this ability generally gets emphasis in certain processes. Level of understanding of Green Accounting can be distinguished on three levels:

- Understanding translation is the ability to understand meaning *Green Accounting* contained there in.
- Interpretive understanding, for example distinguishing two concepts *Green Accounting* different.
- Extrapolation understanding, namely the ability to see behind what is written, implied and explicit, predict something and expand insight about *Green Accounting*.

➤ *The Application of Green Accounting*

The application of Green Accounting is accounting that calculates and includes costs for prevention as well as those incurred as a result of the company's operational activities that affect the environment and society. (Gonzalez and Peña-Vinces, 2022). The application of Green Accounting is a type of environmental accounting that describes efforts to combine environmental benefits and costs into making economic decisions or a business financial result,

The application of Green Accounting describes efforts to incorporate environmental benefits and costs into economic decision-making. The application of Green Accounting is accounting in which it identifies, measures, assesses, and discloses costs related to company activities related to the environment. (Nguyens, 2020). Monsnja and Grzinic (2019), the application of Green Accounting is considered an important tool for understanding aspects of the natural environment that affect the economy and at the same time as an agent of sustainability.

➤ *The Environmental Performance*

According to Rifqi (2018), corporate environmental performance is the performance of a company in creating a good (green) environment. In Indonesia, environmental performance is provided with facilities in the form of a Corporate Performance Rating Program (PROPER) developed by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) since 1995. The aim of PROPER is to encourage companies to improve in terms of environmental management and also to increase the role of companies in managing environment.

➤ *The Influence of the Level of Understanding of Green Accounting on the Financial Statements of SMEs in Bekasi*

According to Monsnja and Grzinic (2019), Green Accounting is considered an important tool for understanding aspects of the natural environment that affect the economy and at the same time as an agent of sustainability. The purpose of Green Accounting/environmental accounting is to inform about the operational performance of companies based on protection and concern for the environment, so that companies cannot process resources arbitrarily without regard to the impact on society.

This understanding is proven by the owners of fashion SMEs who know about business costs, environmental costs and the separation of personal costs from business costs, they do this as a form of responsibility as social beings who must always care and be aware of the importance of maintaining social and environmental conditions. around. Even though the details of business expenses and environmental costs are not understood/know in detail, SMEs already understand that environmental costs are the responsibility of being charged to the business's financial reports. Fashion SME owners in Bekasi must understand business costs, environmental costs and the separation of personal costs from business costs. This more or less influences the concern of business owners in protecting the

environment around their business. In the absence of separation of personal and business expenses due to the ignorance of business owners, the impact on the management of business costs and environmental costs makes financial reports more correct, especially financial performance. Based on this description, the hypotheses that can be proposed in this study are:

H1: The level of understanding of Green Accounting affects the financial statements of SMEs in Bekasi.

➤ *The Application of Green Accounting to SME Financial Statements in Bekasi*

Application *Green Accounting* also aims to find out how much environmental costs are incurred in managing this waste using an accounting system so as to minimize costs incurred (Islamey, 2016).

In implementing Green Accounting, the company carries out various efforts to manage and preserve the environment to achieve green and good environmental performance. Forms of efforts made are to make operational activity efficiency and reduce energy consumption. Based on this description, the hypotheses that can be proposed in this study are:

H2: The level of application of Green Accounting affects the financial statements of SMEs in Bekasi.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative method with an explanatory research approach. The place where the research was carried out was SMEs in Bekasi, especially SMEs engaged in the fashion sector. The research schedule will be conducted from May to July 2023. Types of research data include:

- Primary data in this study were obtained from the results of questionnaires from respondents as a basis for analyzing the level of understanding and application of Green Accounting and SMEs.
- Secondary data is data needed in research to complement the information obtained from primary data sources. The secondary data of this research includes the financial statements of SMEs for 2022 - 2023.

Based on data from the Bekasi Cooperative Office on January 1 2023, the number of fashion SMEs registered in Bekasi is 70 SMEs but 53 fashion SMEs are still active. PThe population in this study were 70 fashion SMEs in Bekasi.

The technique of determining the sample uses Convenience Sampling, namely sampling based on the convenience of the researcher (Mustafa, 2010). The number of research samples is 53 fashion SMEs that are still active in producing activities.

- The independent variable or independent variable in this study is the level of understanding of Green Accounting (X1) and the application of Green Accounting (X2).

- The dependent variable in this study is the financial statements of UKM fashion (Y).

The use of descriptive statistical methods using distribution tables for the answers of managers in large and medium industries related to environmental problems in their area.

The regression test is used to provide a clear picture of the effect of the independent variables used on the dependent variable which will be tested using statistical techniques using a model. The analytical method to find out the independent variables that significantly affect the general multiple linear regression equation is used for five independent variables to a dependent variable, the general multiple regression model, namely: (Gujarati, 2018).

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Where :

- α = constant
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ and β_5 = regression coefficients
- X_1 =level of understanding of Green Accounting
- X_2 =implementation of Green Accounting
- Y =SME financial reports

The F statistical test basically shows whether all the independent or independent variables included in the model have a joint effect on the dependent or dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018).The significance t test is used to see the significance of the effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) partially.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) essentially measures the ability of the independent variable model to explain the variation of the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted on 53 fashion UKM owners in Bekasi. Fashion UKM owners in Bekasi are dominated by 48-53 years of age with 36%. While the fewest aged between 30-35 years as much as 8%. This shows that fashion SME owners or those who manage finances already have a lot of experience.

Respondents from fashion SMEs who graduated from high school with a percentage of 43% and the second largest percentage were business owners with a Bachelor's degree or more with a percentage of 34%, and the lowest percentage, namely owners with a diploma/academy education with a percentage of 23%.

Classification experience of the fashion SME business field tends to influence gender. The results of the distribution of respondents recorded that 58% of fashion SME company/business managers were male while 58% of businesses were female by 42%.

Each path tested shows the influence of understanding Green Accounting and applying Green Accounting to the financial statements of Bekasi fashion SMEs. Based on these results, it is known that the magnitude of direct and indirect influence and the total influence of understanding Green Accounting (X_1) and the application of Green Accounting (X_2) as independent variables on financial statements (Y). The results of multiple linear regression analysis and hypothesis testing are explained in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Path Coefficient Values and Hypothesis Testing

hypothesis	Variable	Variable	Unstandard (β)	t-count	ρ -values
	Free	Bound			
	Constant		13,592	2,542	0.014
1	Understanding of Green Accounting (X1)	Financial report (Y)	0.045	4,380	0.006
2	Implementation of Green Accounting (X2)	Financial report (Y)	0.437	4,146	0.000

Description: = Significant at $\alpha = 5\%$

Based on the results of the regression coefficient, it can be used as a model as follows.

$$Y = 13.592 + 0.045X_1 + 0.437X_2 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

This equation can be interpreted as follows.

- A constant of 13.592 means that if the variable understanding of Green Accounting and the application of Green Accounting is zero or constant, then the financial

statements of UKM Fashion applying Green Accounting are getting better.

- The regression coefficient of 0.045 means that if the Green Accounting application variable is zero or constant, the better the understanding of Green Accounting, the better the financial statements of Fashion SMEs will be.
- The regression coefficient of 0.437 means that if the variable understanding of Green Accounting is zero or

constant, if the application of Green Accounting is getting better, the financial statements of UKM Fashion are also getting better.

Based on Table 4.7, it is obtained that the beta coefficient (β) is equal to 0.045, with a p -value of 0.006. Because the p -value $< \alpha$ or $0.006 < 0.050$, then H1 is accepted. Thus the hypothesis which states that the understanding factor of Green Accounting has a positive influence on financial statements is accepted.

Based on Table 4.7, it is obtained that the beta coefficient (β) is equal to 0.437 with a p -value of 0.000. Because the p -value $< \alpha$ or $0.000 < 0.050$, then H2 is accepted. Thus the hypothesis which states that the understanding factor of Green Accounting has a positive influence on financial statements is accepted.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) basically measures how far the independent variable model's ability to explain the variation of the dependent variable. The result of the coefficient of determination is 0.524 or 52.45%, which means that the proportion of joint influence is 55.6% and the remaining 44.4%.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data analysis, the results of the research can be explained as follows.

➤ *The Level of Understanding of Green Accounting in the Financial Statements of Fashion Small and Medium Enterprises in Bekasi.*

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis it was explained that the respondents' answers regarding the level of understanding of Green Accounting had eight (8) assessment indicators. The average result of the respondents' answers answered that they agreed.

The results show that the level of understanding of Green Accounting in Bekasi fashion SMEs has a good assessment. This is evidenced by the answers of some respondents who answered agree. Means everything that is felt, perceived by respondents about the level of understanding of Green Accounting in Bekasi fashion SMEs.

According to Monsnja and Grzinic (2019), Green Accounting is considered an important tool for understanding aspects of the natural environment that affect the economy and at the same time as an agent of sustainability. The purpose of Green Accounting/environmental accounting is to inform about the operational performance of companies based on protection and concern for the environment, so that companies cannot process resources arbitrarily without regard to the impact on society.

The level of understanding of Green Accounting is more on the development of business cost knowledge which is the sacrifice of business owners for their economic resources which

can be measured in units of money, which have occurred or may still occur for certain purposes. According to Hansen and Mowen (2009) knowledge of business costs includes costs incurred to support activities carried out by business units and to finance the impacts that arise as a result of business operations. This knowledge includes the ability of business actors to identify costs that arise in the production process so that they can accurately calculate their profits

Besides that, understanding *Green Accounting* including knowledge of environmental costs is defined as the knowledge of business actors regarding environmental costs, as well as the imposition of environmental costs in determining business expenses that are calculated/dispensed in financing their business operations. According to Hansen and Mowen (2009) it is said that knowledge of environmental costs includes costs incurred for activities carried out such as disposing of waste or garbage into the environment.

➤ *Application of Green Accounting in the Financial Statements of Fashion Small and Medium Enterprises in Bekasi.*

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis, it was explained that the level of implementation of Green Accounting was based on the average results of the respondents' answers, most of them agreed with 49.76%, while a small number of respondents disagreed with 1.90%.

Based on the overall results of the respondents' answers, it shows that the level of implementation of Green Accounting in Bekasi fashion SMEs has a good rating. This is evidenced by the answers of some respondents who answered strongly agree. Means everything that is felt, perceived by respondents about the level of implementation of Green Accounting in Bekasi fashion SMEs.

The application of Green Accounting in companies can improve the environmental performance of fashion SMEs which ends in improving financial performance with environmental benefits that can be managed and preserved properly according to government regulations. The application of Green Accounting will encourage the ability to minimize environmental problems faced by fashion SMEs. The purpose of implementing environmental accounting is to increase the efficiency of environmental management by carrying out environmental activities from a cost and benefit or effect perspective (Santi, 2016).

➤ *The Influence of the Level of Understanding of Green Accounting on the Financial Statements of SMEs in Bekasi*

Based on the test results it is explained that the understanding of Green Accounting has a positive influence on financial statements so that the first hypothesis is accepted. This shows that the higher the level of understanding of Green Accounting has a positive effect on financial reports.

These results are consistent with Monsnja and Grzinic (2019), Green Accounting is considered an important tool for understanding aspects of the natural environment that affect the economy and at the same time as an agent of sustainability. Fashion UKM owners in Bekasi must understand business costs, environmental costs and the separation of personal costs from business costs. This more or less influences the concern of business owners in protecting the environment around the business so that it has an impact on managing business costs and environmental costs so that financial reports are more correct, especially financial performance.

➤ *The Effect of Green Accounting Implementation on the Financial Statements of SMEs in Bekasi*

Based on the test results, it is explained that the application of Green Accounting has a positive influence on financial statements so that the second hypothesis is accepted. This shows that the higher the level of application of Green Accounting has a positive effect on financial reports.

The results of study are consistent with Islamey (2016) which explains the purpose of implementation *Green Accounting* to find out the environmental costs incurred by SMEs in managing this waste by using an accounting system so as to minimize costs incurred in caring for the environment.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMENDATIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion that has been done, the conclusions in this study are 1) The level of understanding of Green Accounting has a positive effect on the financial statements of Bekasi fashion SMEs. This shows that the higher the level of understanding of Green Accounting has a positive effect on financial statements; 2) The application of Green Accounting has a positive influence on the financial statements of Bekasi fashion SMEs. This shows that the higher the level of implementation of Green Accounting has a positive effect on financial statements.

Based on the research results, there are several suggestions that can be submitted by the author as follows 1) SMEs increase understanding by increasing the level of education and knowledge and experience in managing business costs and environmental costs; 2) SMEs and the government increase socialization cooperation from the government and related parties to socialize the importance of a business protecting the environment around its business by properly managing business costs and environmental costs as a form of implementing Green Accounting and for further research it can be carried out on other business objects and can be done on a wider research sample so that the research results obtained are better and more accurate.

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